

Applying Digital Twins to Optical Networks with Cloud-native SDN Controllers and Generative AI (Invited Paper)

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Abstract This paper presents optical networks using Network Digital Twins (NDT) integrated with cloud-native SDN controllers and intent based networking with generative AI. The framework optimizes network design, automation, and maintenance, enhancing efficiency and performance. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

With the advent of technologies such as 5G and Internet of Things (IoT), vertical industries are experiencing dramatic shifts. Manual processes are increasingly being replaced by digital processes, significantly enhancing efficiency and capability. Central to this transformation is the concept of the Digital Twin (DT), which serves as a real-time representation of physical entities in the digital world. Digital Twins provide virtual-reality interrelation and real-time interaction, enabling iterative operations and process optimization. These capabilities have already been successfully applied in intelligent manufacturing, smart city development, and the operation and maintenance of complex systems. In the context of networking, the Network Digital Twin (NDT) is a digital representation of a data or enterprise network, designed to replicate and represent its physical counterpart virtually. This includes robust capabilities for analysis, decision-making, and intent-based actions. Figure 1 illustrates the concept and functionality of a Network Digital Twin (NDT) system, emphasizing its integration with physical networks and its utilization of artificial intelligence (AI).

A key feature of the NDT is its integration with Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI enhances the NDT by providing advanced analytical capabilities, decision-making processes, and automated optimizations. The AI component ensures that the NDT is not merely a static replica but an active system capable of real-time interaction, iterative operations, and process optimization.

Network Digital Twin has multiple functionalities. It provides a real-time representation: The NDT provides a virtual model of the physical network, enabling real-time interaction and visualization of network states. It supports iterative operations: The NDT can simulate various scenarios and operations iteratively, allowing for testing and validation before implementing changes in the physical network. This capability reduces the risk of potential issues arising from network modifications. And it

Fig. 1: Network Digital Twin.

also allows process optimization: By leveraging AI, the NDT continuously optimizes network operations, enhancing performance and efficiency while reducing the need for manual intervention. AI-driven analysis helps predict issues, propose solutions, and streamline network management processes.

Optical Network Digital Twins

Optical NDT covers novel network use cases.

a) *Enhanced Design and Performance*: Allows testing network configurations virtually before making real-world changes, enabling identification of bottlenecks and optimal resource allocation for robust performance under any condition. This proactive approach minimizes risks and ensures informed decision-making.

b) *Automation*: Automation of repetitive tasks like configuration management and fault detection. Additionally, continuous monitoring and automatic adjustments minimize manual intervention, improve response times, and guarantee consistent policy application, leading to a more efficient and reliable network.

c) *Traffic Management*: Provides real-time insights into traffic patterns and proactively plan for future demands. Simulates traffic scenarios to predict the impact of changes and optimize resource allocation, ensuring smooth operation without congestion.

d) *Simplified Maintenance*: Optical NDT's predictive maintenance capabilities analyze network

data to achieve this, reducing downtime and maintenance costs. It also provides a safe environment to test configuration changes virtually, minimizing errors and ensuring smoother operations.

e) *Security*: Simulate cyberattacks to test and refine security strategies, continuously monitor network activity for anomalies, and develop robust defense mechanisms. This proactive approach offered by Optical NDT keeps your network secure against evolving threats.

f) *Equipment Management*: It models the network's current state and future needs to identify equipment requiring replacement. Simulating the impact of new equipment ensures compatibility and performance improvements.

The Network Digital Twin (NDT) is powered by a suite of enabling technologies that work together to create a comprehensive and dynamic virtual representation of physical networks.

1) *Data Collection and Data Services* gather real-time data from the network, providing the raw information needed for accurate modeling. One key enabler for Optical Network Digital Twin is Data Collection with ONF Transport API Streaming Telemetry. ONF TR-548 introduces a streaming mechanism designed to facilitate a continuous and reliable flow of information between systems.^[1] has demonstrated how this enabler can be used to obtain streaming telemetry.

2) *Network Modeling* uses the received data to create detailed, dynamic simulations of the network's behavior and performance. Several tools facilitate this process, providing robust platforms for simulating network behavior and performance. Mininet^[2] is a widely-used network emulator that creates realistic virtual networks, enabling the testing of network applications, SDN controllers, and network protocols. Containerlab^[3] extends this capability by leveraging container-based virtualization, allowing for the emulation of complex network topologies with high scalability and flexibility. Kubernetes Network Emulation^[4] integrates network emulation within Kubernetes environments, supporting the deployment of network functions as containerized applications, which is essential for modern cloud-native network architectures. Optical-mininet^[5] specifically focuses on the emulation of optical networks, providing tools to simulate and test optical network elements and behaviors. Together, these tools offer a comprehensive suite for network modeling, essential for developing, validating, and optimizing the performance of Network Digital Twins in optical network environments.

3) *Twinning Management* oversees the entire process, ensuring that the digital twin remains synchronized with the physical network, maintaining accuracy and reliability. ETSI TeraFlowSDN is a

key enabler for optical network digital twin, as it is an open-source cloud native SDN Controller enabling smart connectivity services for future networks. It is expected to support twinning management as it can be used as a Network Automation Framework^[6].

4) *Network Visualization* tools transform these models into intuitive visual representations, making it easier for network operators to understand and interact with the network's state.

5) *Interfaces* ensure seamless integration between the NDT and other network management systems, enabling efficient data exchange and control.

An architecture for NDT

Figure 2 presents a proposed network architecture that integrates optical NDT and their interactions within a software-defined networking (SDN) multi-layer network in ADRENALINE Testbed^[7]. This architecture is designed to manage both IP and optical network segments, leveraging advanced technologies such as Kubernetes (K8s), optical SDN orchestration, and network digital twins (NDT) for optimized network performance and management. Previous versions of this architecture have been presented by authors in^[8] and^[9].

The End-to-End TeraFlowSDN (TFS) Orchestrator (Network Automation Framework) comprises several core modules to handle different aspects of network management. It is able to handle IP over DWDM network scenarios. The IP SDN Controller manages the IP-based network segments, connecting with Edge Data Center Controllers (EdgeDC-5 and EdgeDC-6). These edge data centers utilize Kubernetes (K8s) for container orchestration. On the optical side, the Optical SDN Controller oversees the optical network segments, interacting with physical optical components like Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (ROADMs). To ensure comprehensive network management, the E2E TFS orchestrator incorporates several critical modules. The NDT module plays a crucial role by simulating the physical network, allowing for thorough testing and validation of network changes before they are implemented. This ensures that any modifications do not adversely affect the network's performance.

The lifecycle of a Network Digital Twin (NDT) begins with deployment, where the NDT subscribes to Kafka to receive topology information from the physical SDN controller through ONF TAPI streaming. The Optical Line System (OLS) then publishes the network topology, enabling the deployment of virtual SDN controllers and virtual optical nodes. During the update phase, the SDN controller publishes any changes or updates using ONF TAPI streaming, prompting the NDT to reconfigure its virtual nodes, including updating telemetry data.

Fig. 2: Proposed architecture for Network Digital Twin.

In the operation phase, connectivity services can be tested, where the SDN controller evaluates the feasibility of these services, possibly using a Quality of Transmission (QoT) estimator. Only feasible connectivity services are applied to the network. Finally, the removal phase involves decoupling and stopping the NDT, ensuring it is properly disconnected from the network. This comprehensive lifecycle ensures that the NDT remains an accurate and effective representation of the physical network, facilitating advanced testing, validation, and optimization of network services.

Generative Artificial Intelligence and Network Digital Twins

Intent-based networking (IBN) allows users to input their abstract 'intent' to the network instead of detailing specific policies or configurations on network devices. A key feature of an IBN system is its ability to automatically ensure user intent by continuously adjusting policies and validating real-time network conditions. In the context of a network digital twin, IBN can significantly enhance the efficiency of deploying network intents. By simulating several rounds of adjustments and validations on the digital twin platform, the impact on actual networks is minimized. Therefore, a network digital twin serves as a crucial platform for implementing IBN systems and facilitating their deployment.

IBN requires integration of a large language model (LLM) in order to process natural language into network actions. The authors have presented

a chatbot within the TeraFlowSDN framework that marks a significant advancement in intent-based networking^[10]. This chatbot, known as IntentLLM, is integrated with TeraFlowSDN and it interprets user prompts and converts them into transport slice requests, demonstrating the creation and management of new network slices in real-time. This development builds on previous work in intent-based networking by incorporating more sophisticated natural language processing capabilities, allowing the chatbot to understand context, synonyms, and provide detailed explanations of network intents.

Conclusion

This paper has explored the innovative application of Network Digital Twins (NDT) integrated with cloud-native SDN controllers and generative AI within optical networks. The presented framework demonstrates significant potential for optimizing network design, automation, and maintenance, offering enhanced efficiency and performance. The integration of large language models (LLMs) into this framework further enhances its capabilities, allowing for intuitive, natural language interactions and automated network management. This approach not only simplifies user interactions but also ensures that the network can adapt dynamically. Through comprehensive simulations, real-time monitoring, and proactive maintenance, the optical NDT framework can significantly reduce operational costs, improve overall network reliability.

Acknowledgements

The research leading to this publication has been partially financed by the Horizon Europe COBALT Project (grant agreement No. 101119602) and by Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital and the European Union-Next GenerationEU in the frameworks of the Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia and of the Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia through UNICO-5G I+D 6GMICROSDN project under references TSI-063000-2021-19, TSI-063000-2021-20, TSI-063000-2021-21 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER/UE and by the RELAMPAGO project (Grant PID2021-127916OB-I00), funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU.

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